

THE DIFFICULTIES TO DEVELOP SPEAKING SKILL FOR EFL STUDENTS

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Abstract: When you going to another countries or watching English blockbuster movies, you can feel yourself that you are not good at English exactly. However, there is painful truth which is included some number of certain problems. We can say that language barrier is the most problematic situation when you are in overseas or for EFL students. In this article we will try to find the difficulties and their vivid solutions to develop speaking skill for EFL students.

Key words: speaking skill, EFL-ESL learners, aspects, the scoring rubric of speaking.

INTRODUCTION

Speaking is the most important type of communication between people. Of course, it may seem as easy as pie for everyone at first sight to keep in contact with others in native language. But, actually, it is not. It requires to be eloquent person to find suitable words, phrases in a minute. It is clear that you might lose yourself during the speaking in your mother tongue. However, what about speaking in another language? Actually, it is also another the most challenging problem.

First of all, we have to differentiate the terms of ESL and EFL. Even though they seem very similar, there are some differences between them. ESL (English as a second language) refers to learners who are using English in order to communicate in a second language. On the other hand, EFL (English as a foreign language) learners are those who are studying English in a non-native country. English in Uzbekistan is a foreign language and mostly school pupils still learn it. But they come across some challenges during the learning.

Along with increasing awareness to be able to communicate in English, EFL students have been exposed to English since they were in elementary school. However, the majority of English learners are incapable of oral communication (Zhang, 2009)

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

So, there is a question: “Why learning speaking skills are difficult for EFL students?”. We may find lots of answers in here. First of all, students will suffer from six aspects of speaking skill, namely, pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, fluency, comprehension and task. These six components of speaking assessment proposed by Brown (2004)

Table 1. The scoring rubric of speaking (Brown: 2001)

Aspect	Score	Description
Pronunciation	1	Errors in pronunciation are frequent but can be understood by a native speaker used to dealing with foreigners attempting to speak his language.
	2	The accent is intelligible though often quite faulty.
	3	Errors never interfere with understanding and rarely disturb the native speaker. The accent may be obviously foreign.
	4	Errors in pronunciation are quite rare.
	5	Equivalent to and fully accepted by educated native speakers.
Grammar	1	Errors in grammar are frequent, but the speaker can be understood by a native speaker.
	2	Can usually handle elementary construction quite accurately but does not have thorough or confident control of the grammar.
	3	Control of grammar is good. Able to speak the language with sufficient structural accuracy to participate effectively in most formal and informal conversations on practical, social, and professional topics.
	4	Able to use the language accurately on all levels normally pertinent to professional needs. Errors in grammatical are quite rare.
	5	Equivalent to that of an educated native speaker.
Vocabulary	1	Speaking vocabulary inadequate to express anything but the most elementary needs.
	2	Has speaking vocabulary sufficient to express himself simply with some circumlocutions.
	3	Able to speak the language with sufficient vocabulary to participate effectively in most formal and informal conversations on practical, social, and professional topics. The vocabulary used is broad enough that he rarely has to grope for a word.
	4	Can understand and participate in any conversation within the range of his experience with a high degree of precision in vocabulary.
	5	Speech on all levels is fully accepted by educated native speakers in all its features including breadth of vocabulary and idioms, colloquialisms, and pertinent cultural references.
Fluency	1	(No specific fluency description. Refer to the other four language areas for the implied level of fluency)
	2	Can handle with confidence but not with facility most situations, including introductions and casual conversation about current events, as well as work, family, and autobiographical information.
	3	Can discuss particular interests of competence with reasonable ease. Rarely has to grope for words.
	4	Able to use the language fluently on all levels normally pertinent to professional needs. Can participate in any conversation within the range of the experience with a high degree of fluency.
	5	Has complete fluency in the language such that his speech is fully accepted by educated native speakers.

Comprehension	1	Within the scope of his very limited language experience, can understand simple questions and statements if delivered with slowed speech, repetition, or paraphrase.
	2	Can get the gist of most conversations on non-technical subjects (i.e., topics that require no specialised knowledge)
	3	Comprehension is quite complete at a normal rate of speech.
	4	Can understand any conversation within the range of his experience.
	5	Equivalent to that of an educated native speaker.
Task	1	Can ask and answer questions on topics very familiar to him. Able to satisfy routine travel needs and minimum courtesy requirements (should be able to order-simple directions, make purchases and tell time)
	2	Able to satisfy routine social demands and work requirements; needs help in handling any complications or difficulties.
	3	Can participate effectively in most formal and informal conversations on practical, social, and professional topics.
	4	Would rarely be taken for a native speaker but can respond to appropriately even in unfamiliar situations. Can handle informal interpreting forms and into language.
	5	Speaking proficiency is equivalent to that of an educated native speaker.

Thoroughly, the scoring rubric for speaking skills is given in this table.

The distinction has become difficult to sustain, however for two reasons. Firstly, many communities- whether in English or non-English speaking countries are now multilingual and English is a language of communication. Does that make it a foreign or a second language? Secondly, however, many students of EFL use English in a global context as we have seen. (Harmer, 2005)

CONCLUSION

To conclude, every EFL students think that speaking is one of the impossible process, but, actually, it is not. Just lack of knowledge and motivation, language barrier, reading laziness or shyness, less dictionary usage will cause to appear some difficulties in speaking. However, the only way to achieve the impossible is to believe it is possible.

References:

1. A.Normawati, Dwitiya, Noor Sahid, A.Susanto// Article of EFL learners' difficulties in speaking English- Article of Electrum the English language and education spectrum.- Indanesia,2023.
2. Harmer,Jeremy.// The practice of English language teaching.- Cambridge:Cambridge University Press,2005.
3. Brown,H.D.// Language assessment:Principles and classroom practice. - New York,Longman, 2004.
4. Zhang.S // the role of input, interaction and output in the development of oral fluency- English language teaching.2(4),91-100. 2009.